

LECTURERS' PERCEPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS FOR TALENT ACQUISITION EFFECTIVENESS IN RIVERS STATE UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated lecturers' perception of artificial intelligence tools in enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The total population of the study was 1,481 lecturers in Rivers State Universities, from which a sample size of 285 respondents (150 males and 135 females) was randomly selected. The instrument for the study was a self-structured questionnaire titled: "Lecturers Perception of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Talent Acquisition Effectiveness Questionnaire" which was based on a 4-point rating scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. The instrument was face and content validated by two experts from Measurement and Evaluation and the Department of Educational Management. The test for reliability was established using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding coefficients of .79, .82 and .84. The research questions were answered with mean and standard deviation while z-test was employed to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Findings revealed that lecturers were of the perception that AI resume screening tools are fair to identify the most qualified candidates, AI chatbots are effective in reducing administrative workload and AI video interviewing platforms are useful for improving the quality of hires. It also indicated no statistically significant difference between male and female lecturers' perceptions of artificial intelligence tools for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Based on these findings, it was recommended that government and university management should invest in AI-enabled hiring systems that should be seamlessly integrated in their existing infrastructure for transparency, efficiency and fairness.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Talent Acquisition, Lecturers, Recruitment, Higher Education.

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INTRODUCTION

Universities serve as centers of knowledge production, innovation, and intellectual leadership. To sustain this role, they must attract and retain top talents who can contribute meaningfully to institutional development, national progress and global competitiveness. The need for effective, timely and unbiased talent acquisition process for higher education is therefore not a peripheral task, but a strategy for the survival and excellence of higher institutions. In universities, all over the world, the quality of academic and administrative staff positively influences educational standards, research output, and institutional competitiveness. The developed countries of the world in pursuance of excellence in recruitment and selection processes of human resources have decided on top talent acquisition schemes through innovative technology. However, in Nigeria, traditional methods of talent acquisition often characterized by manual processes, limited automation, and bureaucratic bottlenecks are still in practice, despite been criticized for inefficiency, lack of transparency and vulnerability to favoritism (Abaiola & Nwafor, 2021; Don-Baridam et al., 2022). This outdated approach hinders the timely and effective onboarding of qualified professionals and undermines the broader goal of academic excellence. Given the growing demand for competent and innovative professionals in higher education, talent acquisition must move beyond traditional methods. To meet this need, advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) now offer universities the tools to modernize and optimize their recruitment process. These include AI-driven resume screening systems such as predictive analytics, chatbots, and video interviewing platforms; all of which are reshaping how institutions attract and select top talents (Raji et al., 2024).

Artificial intelligence, broadly defined, refers to computers that are capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making (Amie-Ogan, 2025; Russo et al., 2025). Furthermore, Widodo et al. (2023), explained that AI technologies can also perceive their environment, recognize patterns and objects and learn from past experiences, capabilities that support problem-solving and decision-making functions. Abraham et al. (2025) highlighted the use of these technologies in human resource management as streamlining talent acquisition processes by automating repetitive tasks, enhancing candidate experience, and promoting data-driven hiring decisions. They explained that AI resume screening tools rapidly scan applications, extract key qualifications and may review candidates' public online profiles to support informed shortlisting; chatbots engage applicants in real time, streamlining communication and improving their overall experience; while video interviewing platforms analyze candidates' recorded responses, evaluating verbal cues, language use and behavioral indicators, to identify strong candidates ahead of human interviews. Bedi et al. (2024) further emphasized that AI can reduce bias, save time and improve the alignment between candidate capabilities and job requirements. These advancements position AI as a powerful tool for improving talent acquisition effectiveness in modern institutions, including universities.

Talent acquisition is distinct from routine recruitment. Sahana and Pallavi (2023) viewed recruitment as a short-term, reactive process aimed at filling immediate vacancies, while talent acquisition is a strategic, long-term approach that involves identifying, attracting, assessing, hiring and onboarding highly qualified individuals to meet an institution's current and future workforce needs. Talent acquisition involves proactively identifying an organization's staffing needs and determining how prospective employees will align with its goals and structure upon engagement. It goes beyond filling vacancies by integrating workforce planning, employer

branding, and candidate relationship management; making it a core part of any university's talent management strategy (Abaiola & Nwafor, 2021). In academic institutions, effective talent acquisition ensures that hires are not only well-qualified but also positioned for future leadership and contribution to institutional growth. Talent acquisition effectiveness refers to how well an institution can attract, identify, and hire suitable candidates for available positions within an appropriate timeframe. It is often evaluated based on metrics such as time-to fill, quality-of-hire, cost-per-hire and candidate satisfaction (Sjahrudin et al., 2024). AI is increasingly recognized as a valuable solution for improving these key indicators, especially within large and complex institutions like universities. It streamlines and automates the bulk of the recruitment process through resume screening tools, chatbots, and video interviewing platforms, significantly reducing manual workload.

In Nigeria's higher education context, particularly in Rivers State Universities (Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education), the adoption of AI in human resource functions remain emergent. Private organizations may have embraced AI solutions more rapidly but public universities are debarred by infrastructural, financial and cultural barriers. It is essential to explore how lecturers, as key stakeholders in higher institutions (who are not only end-users of recruitment outcomes but are often involved in hiring processes, policy formulation and departmental staffing decisions) could perceive AI tools to enhance talent acquisition effectiveness. A positive perception may foster the adoption of AI technologies in university recruitment while skepticism or resistance may hinder it. Perception, in this context, involves how lecturers interpret and assess the relevance, efficiency, fairness and reliability of AI-driven recruitment systems.

AI resume screening tools utilize natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning algorithms to extract relevant data such as skills, qualifications and experience from applicants' resumes, enabling recruiters to identify top candidates quickly and objectively (Bedi et al, 2024). These tools aim to reduce time-to-hire and mitigate human bias in initial screening, making them a cornerstone of modern talent acquisition (Villeda, 2025). Utilization of AI tools in organisations for recruitment has proven their effectiveness. To buttress the afore statement, Unilever adopted AI screening tools such as Pymetrics and HireVue in 2017 to process over 200,000 applications which resulted in a 50% reduction in hiring time and increased in diverse hires by minimizing subjective judgments (Black & van Esch, 2020). They reviewed several organizations and found that AI screening improved hiring accuracy by 25% compared to manual methods, with faster processing (from days to hours) and saving cost in large scale recruitments. Similarly, Amazon's Amazon Q tool, used for entry-level roles, screened millions of resumes, achieving a 20% improvement in candidate quality as measured by retention rates post-hire (Dastin, 2018). However, Abraham et al. (2025) and O'Brien and Downie (2025) cautioned on limitations such as algorithmic bias, where tools trained on historical data perpetrate gender or racial disparities. For instance, a 2018 study by Amazon revealed biases against women in tech roles, leading to tool discontinuation. Research by Raghavan, Barocas, Kleinberg and Levy (2020) emphasized the need for bias audits and diverse training data to enhance fairness. Overall, AI resume screening tools significantly boost efficiency and objectivity in talent acquisition, but their effectiveness hinges on ethical oversight and continuous refinement.

AI-powered chatbots facilitates initial candidate interactions by automating inquiries, scheduling interviews and providing job information, enhancing engagement and scalability in talent acquisition (Thangaraj & Prakash, 2024; Abraham et al., 2025). Instances of this nature

abound in IBM Watsonx and Unilever. IBM Watsonx chatbot deployed for recruitment did not only cut costs but handled candidate queries autonomously, by reducing process times by 40% (IBM, 2020). Likewise, Unilever during a recruitment, processed about 1.8 million job applicants, by using their Unabot which enabled them to achieve a rise in qualified applicant pools and higher satisfaction scores (Marr, 2018). Raji et al. (2024) and Tiwari and Natal (2025) noted that chatbots increased conversation rates from inquiries to applications by 50%, which resulted in reduced wait times and proactive guidance. However, some studies have raised concerns about chatbots being perceived as impersonal, and therefore could be problematic in academic settings where relational trust, human interaction and professional rapport are highly valued (Tiwari & Natal, 2025). Thus, the effectiveness of AI chatbots in talent acquisition depends on how well they balance automation with human-centered communication.

AI video interview platforms are tools which use artificial intelligence to evaluate candidates' responses through pre-recorded video submissions which often use algorithms to assess verbal and non-verbal cues such as facial expressions, speech patterns and eye movement to evaluate traits like confidence, honesty and emotional intelligence (Bedi et al., 2024; Raghavan et al., 2020). Examples include Affectiva, HireIQ, and HireVue which use AI-powered keyword analysis (Meshram, 2023). Companies such as Unilever and Goldman Sachs employed HireVue's platform to analyze video interviews for 500,000+ candidates, resulting in a more efficient, scalable and standardized initial screening process. Similarly, Accenture employed Pymetrics AI-driven video assessments and recorded an enhanced diversity in hires by focusing on cognitive and emotional traits (Garfield, 2017). Scholars argue that such systems may be of a disadvantage to candidates from different cultural or linguistic backgrounds or those with disabilities that affect non-verbal communication (Raghavan et al., 2020). In addition to these inclusive challenges, issues of transparency, data privacy, and algorithmic bias must also be addressed to ensure responsible and equitable adoption of such technologies (Thangaraj & Prakash, 2024). AI video platforms are highly effective for scalable, data-driven talent acquisition, provided they are used ethically and in conjunction with human judgment.

Statement of the Problem

Recruiting and retaining high-caliber academics is critical to the mission and vision of universities. However, university hiring processes often face serious setbacks as academic vacancies typically attract large volumes of applications from individuals with varying levels of competence and experience, whereby in some cases, candidates rely on cronyism rather than on meritocracy. Aside from the aforementioned, screening numerous applications manually during a selection process is labor-intensive, time consuming, create delays and increases the likelihood of inconsistency, human error, or bias during selection. Rivers State owned universities continue to struggle with prolonged hiring cycles, manual and inconsistent shortlisting procedures, limited transparency, inadequate documentation and subjective evaluations of applicants. These factors that bedevil the selection process contribute to mismatches between job requirements and selected candidates, slow down the filling of critical positions and breeds dissatisfaction among stakeholders involved in the recruitment process.

Given these challenges, it is noteworthy that in the 21st Century universities endeavour to integrate AI tools in their recruitment and selection processes so as to be at par with their counterparts all over the world. It is against this background that the study investigated lecturers'

perception of artificial intelligence tools for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate lecturers' perception of artificial intelligence tools for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Determine male and female lecturers' perception of AI-powered resume screening tools for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- Examine male and female lecturers' perception of AI-powered chatbots for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- Ascertain male and female lecturers' perception of AI-powered video interview platforms for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- What is the perception of male and female lecturers on the use of AI-powered resume screening tools for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?
- What is the perception of male and female lecturers on the use of AI-powered chatbots for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?
- What is the perception of male and female lecturers on the use of AI-powered video interview platforms for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses further guided the study:

- There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered resume screening tools for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered chatbots for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
- There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered video interviewing platforms for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population comprised all lecturers in Rivers State universities: 1,095 from Rivers State University (RSU) and 386 from Ignatius

Ajuru University of Education (IAUE), giving a total of 1,481 lecturers. From this population, a sample of 285 lecturers were selected. This sample included 150 male lecturers (120 from RSU and 30 from IAUE) and 135 female lecturers (108 from RSU and 27 from IAUE). The sample size was above 10% of the population, which is considered adequate according to Nwana as cited in Kpee (2015). Simple random sampling technique was adopted for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled “Lecturers Perception of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Talent Acquisition Effectiveness in Rivers State Universities Questionnaire (LPAITTAEQ)”, based on four-point rating scale of : Strongly Agree (SA)- 4, Agree (A) - 3, Disagree (D) - 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha, which yielded reliability indexes of 0.79, 0.82 and 0.84. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Mean scores of 2.50 and above denoted ‘Agree’ and below 2.50 depicted ‘Disagree’. The hypotheses were tested using z-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. Analyzed data with a z-calculated value within the range of the z-critical value of ± 1.96 was accepted while values below the z-critical of ± 1.96 was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the perception of male and female lecturers’ on the use of AI-powered resume screening tools for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of male and female lecturers perception on the use of ai-powered resume screening tools for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State universities

S/N	Items	Male n = 150		Female n = 135		Mean set	Decision
		Mean	SD.	Mean	SD.		
1.	AI resume-screening can accurately match candidates’ qualifications to job requirements	2.95	0.62	2.96	0.70	2.96	Agree
2.	AI resume-screening tools reduce time-to-shortlist candidates’ compared with manual screening	2.95	0.68	2.96	0.74	2.96	Agree
3.	AI resume screeners’ improve fairness by minimizing human bias.	3.00	0.70	3.04	0.64	3.02	Strongly Agree
4.	I trust shortlists generated by AI resume-screening software.	3.07	0.77	3.11	0.80	3.09	Strongly Agree
5.	Implementing AI resume screening would make university recruitment more transparent	3.17	0.75	3.10	0.79	3.14	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean		3.03		3.03		3.03	Strongly Agree

Results from Table 1 showed that all the items were accepted. The respondents agreed that AI-powered resume screening tools promote fairness and transparency to the recruitment process and significantly reduces the time required to shortlist qualified candidates. This is evidenced by the grand mean values of 3.03 for male respondents and 3.03 for female respondents.

Research Question 2: What is the perception of male and female lecturers on the use of AI-powered chatbots for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of male and female lecturers perception on the use of ai-powered chatbots for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	Male n = 150		Female n = 135		Mean set	Decision
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
6.	AI-powered chatbots can improve communication between the university and applicants.	2.94	0.69	2.95	0.70	2.95	Agree
7.	Using AI-powered chatbots would improve candidates' overall experience with the university.	2.89	0.74	3.01	0.73	2.95	Agree
8.	AI powered Chatbots help reduce the administrative workload on human resources staff.	3.26	0.71	3.16	0.63	3.21	Strongly Agree
9.	I believe AI-powered chatbots can screen basic eligibility effectively before human review.	3.07	0.68	3.08	0.74	3.08	Strongly Agree
10.	AI-powered chatbots contribute to a more organized recruitment process.	3.19	0.70	3.16	0.70	3.18	Strongly Agree
11.	AI-powered Chatbots may feel impersonal for academic recruitment	2.99	0.71	3.02	0.72	3.01	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean		3.06		3.06		3.06	Strongly Agree

Results from Table 2 revealed that all the items were accepted, indicating that respondents believe that AI-powered chatbots enhance the efficiency of the recruitment process. Specifically, they agreed that AI-powered chatbots facilitate real-time communication and reduce administrative workload for human resource departments. This perception is reflected in the grand mean values of 3.06 for male and 3.06 for female respondents.

Research Question 3: What is the perception of male and female lecturers on the use of AI-powered video interviewing platforms for enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of male and female lecturers perception on the use of ai-powered video interviewing platforms for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	Male n = 150		Female n = 135		Mean set	Decision
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
12.	AI video interviews allow fair comparison of all candidates.	3.20	0.71	3.19	0.71	3.20	Strongly Agree
13.	Video interviewing platforms reduce logistical burdens for academic hiring panels.	2.99	0.57	3.00	0.64	3.00	Strongly Agree
14.	I trust AI to fairly analyze candidates' non-verbal cues.	3.11	0.68	3.08	0.67	3.10	Strongly Agree
15.	Recorded AI interviews help panels review responses objectively at their convenience.	3.22	0.60	3.09	0.70	3.16	Strongly Agree

16.	AI video interview would enhance the quality of hiring decisions.	3.13	0.75	3.07	0.73	3.10	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean		3.13		3.09		3.11	Strongly Agree

Results from Table 3 showed that all the items were accepted. Respondents agreed that AI-powered video interviewing platforms help improve the quality and fairness of selection by evaluating candidates objectively based on recorded responses and behavioral cues. The results showed grand mean values of 3.13 for male and 3.09 for female respondents respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered resume screening tools for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4: z-test analysis of difference between male and female lecturers perception on the use of AI-powered resume screening tools for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Lecturers	N	Mean	SD	df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male	150	3.03	0.70					
				283	0.05	-0.07	±1.96	Failed to reject
Female	135	3.03	0.73					

Results presented in Table 4 revealed a z-calculated value of -0.07 and 283 as degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no significant difference between the male and female lecturers' perception of AI-powered resume screening tools for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers' perception of AI-powered chatbots for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Table 5: z-test analysis of difference between male and female lecturers perception on the use of AI-powered chatbots for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Lecturers	N	Mean	SD	df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male	150	3.06	0.71					
				283	0.05	-0.08	±1.96	Failed to reject
Female	135	3.06	0.70					

Table 5, unraveled a z-calculated value of -0.08 and a degree of freedom of 283 at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which indicated no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered chatbots in enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered video interviewing platforms for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Table 6: z-test analysis of difference between male and female lecturers perception on the use of AI-powered video interviewing platforms for talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Lecturers	N	Mean	SD	df	α	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male	150	3.13	0.66	283	0.05	0.56	± 1.96	Failed to reject
Female	135	3.09	0.69					

Results in Table 6 indicated a z-calculated value of 0.56 and a degree of freedom of 283 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis was accepted which indicated no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the use of AI-powered video interviewing platforms enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from research question 1 on Table 1 revealed that lecturers perceived that the use of AI-powered resume screening tools enhanced talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities with an average grand mean value of 3.03. These findings are consistent with Raji et al. (2024), who argued that AI resume screening enhances objectivity and minimizes human biases that may influence selection. Similarly, Black and van Esch (2020) asserted that AI tools used for screening do not only reduce administrative burden but also increase the quality and consistency of candidate evaluations. Hypothesis 1 in Table 4 revealed a z-calculated value of -0.07 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance, indicating no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perceptions on the use of AI powered resume screening tools in enhancing talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State. This aligns with Monika and Senthilmathi (2025) who reported no significant gender-based differences in perceptions toward the use of AI technologies in the talent acquisition process. Given that merit, expertise, and transparency are fundamental to the hiring process, lecturers' support for AI resume screening suggests openness toward digital transformation in academic recruitment.

Results from research question 2 on Table 2 showed that lecturers are of the view that AI chatbots serve as valuable tools for improving candidate engagement, streamlining communication and reducing administrative workload of human resource staff. The mean ratings for both male and female lecturers were equally high, indicating strong agreement that chatbots enhance the recruitment experience. This aligns with the findings of Abraham et al. (2025), who highlighted the role of AI chatbots in streamlining communication, answering queries in real-time, and improving the responsiveness of institutions during hiring. Thangaraj and Prakash (2024) further affirmed that the presence of chatbots contribute to an institutions employer brand by portraying it as modern, organized, and candidate-focused. However, Tiwari and Natal (2025) reported that while respondents appreciated the quick responses provided by AI chatbots, 10% expressed dissatisfaction, describing the interaction as impersonal and indicating a preference for more human engagement. Correspondingly hypothesis 2 on Table 5 showed z-calculated value of -0.08 which lies within z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance, indicating no

significant difference between male and female lecturers' perceptions of chatbots usefulness across gender. The finding contradicted the findings of Russo, Romadu, Clemente, Iacovane, Gladwin and Panno (2025), who observed significant gender variations, noting that male respondents generally expressed more positive perceptions of AI than their female counterparts. Lecturers' favorable views of chatbots thus reinforced the importance of adopting technology which balances efficiency with a human-centered approach to hiring.

The findings from research question 3 on Table 3 showed that lecturers agreed that AI video interviewing platforms can improve the quality of hires by enabling more objective candidate evaluations. This finding is in tandem with Kee and Hassan (2025), who noted that video interviewing platforms improve the standardization, scalability of interviews, reduce interviewer fatigue and provide consistent evaluation environments thereby enhancing objectivity of selection outcomes. However, it contradicts the findings of Sjahrudin, Boyas and Prayudi (2024), who found that the application of AI technologies did not have a statistically significant impact on the quality of hires. Hypothesis 3 on Table 6 indicated a z-calculated value of 0.56 which is less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance, indicating no significant difference between the male and female perceptions regarding AI video interviewing platforms across gender. The result corroborates with Monika and Senthilmathi (2025), who reported that gender does not have a significant influence on employees' perceptions of the use of AI usage in talent acquisition. For universities seeking to attract top-tier academic staff, the use of AI video platforms could lead to more informed and unbiased hiring decisions.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that both male and female lecturers generally perceived that AI-powered tools for talent acquisition such as AI-powered resume screening tools, chatbots and video interview platforms would enhance talent acquisition effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

- The government and university managements should prioritize investing in AI-powered resume screening tools to save time as well as deduce relevant data such as skills, qualification, years of experience and competences thereby ensuring the identification of top-tier candidates for universities growth and success.
- Universities management should use AI-powered chatbots to achieve a talented recruitment pool and also orchestrate engagement and scalability in talent acquisition.
- Universities should endeavor to use AI-powered video platforms for talent acquisition for diversity in hires with cognitive and emotional traits on focus

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